

CONSERVATION OF PRIORITY SPECIES OF MARINE MEGAFUNA IN GREECE AND ITALY

D5.1: Leaflet & Banner/Beach flags & T-shirts

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LIFE22-NAT-EL-LIFE MareNatura
“Conservation of priority species of marine megafauna in Greece and Italy”

**Grant Agreement Project 101113792 -
LIFE22-NAT-EL-LIFE MareNatura - LIFE-2022-SAP-NAT**

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Abbreviations

ARCHELON	ARCHELON - The Sea Turtle Protection Society of Greece
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
HCMR	Hellenic Center for Marine Research
HOS	Hellenic Ornithological Society
ISPRA	Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research
MEDASSET	Mediterranean Association to Save the Sea Turtles
MOm	Hellenic Society for the Study and Protection of the Monk Seal
N2K	Natura 2000
NCC	Nature Conservation Consultants
NECCA	Natural Environment and Climate Change Agency
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
T	Task
UoA	University of the Aegean
UoC	University of Crete
WaterProof	Waterproof Marine Consultancy & Services B.V.
WP	Work Package

Summary

This document describes Deliverable D5.1 – Leaflet & Banner/Beach flags & T-shirts, which relates to the production of the LIFE MareNatura general info material. The delivery of the info material is part of Task 5.2 – Overall project communication: project webpage, communication materials, etc., sub-task 5.2.3 – Project’s info material (Brochure, Roll Ups/Beach Flags and T-shirts). The processes involved in the design of the layout and the production of the project’s info material are stated in this report. More specifically the steps taken to the development of the design of info material as well as the technical issues of the final products, are thoroughly discussed.

Production process

Chapter 1: Design of info material (Brochure, Roll-Ups/Beach Flags and T-shirts)

The T.5.2.3 - Development of the info material (Brochure, Roll Ups/Beach Flags and T-shirts) started in accordance with the time schedule of the project.

Preliminary discussions between Communication Leader and the Project Coordinator about the contents of the Brochure, the Roll up and the Beach flag took place during February 2024.

The first draft text of the Brochure as well as a proposal for its dimensions and layout was discussed between the Communication Leader and the Coordinator of the project at the end of March 2024 and the final text with translations in English and Italian was agreed at the end of May 2024. At the same time, the text to be included in the Roll Up/Banner was also discussed and agreed between the responsible partners (UoC and HCMR).

For the design of the info materials a direct treaty procedure was launched in March 2024, with 2 offers to be specifically requested by providers, and the Decision No. 22700/30.04.2024 for the direct treaty to the Contractor "Metrographics" was issued.

All necessary texts, pictures, logos, etc., and general guidelines for the design of the materials were sent to the graphic designer. The first drafts of the T-shirt layout (3 proposals) were received at the end of May 2024. Drafts of the rollups and the Beach flag were received at the beginning of June 2024.

The Communication Team of UoC, the Coordinator, and the Coordinator's Assistant commented on the drafts for improvements and the final maquettes of the T-shirt (1), the Roll Ups (2 bilingual banners: 1 in Greek & English and 1 in Italian & English) and the Beach Flag (1 in English) were agreed and received on May 29, 2024, and June 13, 2024, respectively. By the end of June 2024, the graphic designs were uploaded to the project's repository, and all partners were informed of their completion.

As far as the project's Brochure design is concerned, the 1st draft proposal from the graphic designer was received on June 6, 2024. After some discussions between the Leader Beneficiary and the Coordinator of the Project, changes in the content and the text of the Brochure were

decided during July 2024, something that led to the delay of brochure's layout completion. Considering that August is a holiday month in Greece, the final maquettes (1 in Greek, 1 in English, and 1 in Italian language) were received on August 30, 2024.

All mockups were designed based on the project's visual ID (color palette) and they include the project's logo, LIFE, and Natura 2000 logo. Except for the T-shirt all other products include the project's title, code, acronym, tagline, co-funders logos (Green Fund and A.G. Leventis Institution), and partners' logos. More details for the design of each material can be seen in the following chapter 3.

Chapter 2: Printing of info material (Brochure, Roll-Ups/Beach Flags and T-shirts)

According to the proposal and the GA, UoC is responsible for the layout of all info materials and the printings of the T-shirts (1,500 items), of the brochures (65,000 items in total: 50,000 in Greek, 2,000 in Italian and 13,000 in English) and of one (1) Roll up/banner. Partners who had foreseen a budget for the printing of their banners and flags would produce them separately. The UoC (Leader Beneficiary) decided to print part of the materials due to the limited financial resources of the first payment that should be managed for the period 2024-2026. In this context the following quantities of the info material of the project were produced:

- T-shirts: 1,000 items
- Brochures in Greek: 25,000 items
- Brochures in English: 8,000 items
- Brochures in Italian: 1,000 items

For the printing of the T-shirts and UoC's Roll up/Banner a direct treaty procedure was launched in May 2024, with 2 offers to be specifically requested by providers, and the Decision No. 30454/13.06.2024 for the direct treaty to the Contractor "RODO, Graphic Arts Workshop. Lavrenidi Elpida E." was issued.

For the printing of the brochures a direct treaty procedure was launched in June 2024, with 2 offers to be specifically requested by providers, and the Decision No. 31559/20.06.2024 for the direct treaty to the Contractor "TYPOCRETA. Graphic Arts. G. Kazanakis, Industrial and Commercial SA"

was issued.

The T-shirts and UoC's Roll up/Banner were received on July 12, 2024, and their dissemination to project partners took place on July 31, 2024. All Brochures were received in mid-September 2024 and their dissemination to partners started immediately.

Chapter 3: Project info materials' quality characteristics

T-shirt quality characteristics

Project's T-shirt maquette shows an improvised graphic sketch of a dolphin, project's logo and tagline on the front view and LIFE, Natura 2000 and project's logos on the left sleeve (Picture 1). The maquette is adapted for printing in white and denim blue and its dimensions are 25X30 cm (the front view) and 12X10cm (the sleeve).

Picture 1: T-shirt maquettes in white and denim blue.

All of them are short-sleeved and were printed in 100% cotton weighing 150gr (Picture 2). Their printing was done by silk screen in 3 pantone

colours.

In total 1,000 items were produced: 500 in female form and 500 in male form.

From each form 250 were white and 250 blue denim in all sizes (S, M, L, XL and 2X), as follows:

White T-shirts=500 items

FORM/SIZES	S	M	L	XL	2XL
MALE	25	50	80	45	50
FEMALE	75	75	50	30	20

Denim Blue T-shirts=500 items

FORM/SIZES	S	M	L	XL	2XL
MALE	25	50	80	45	50
FEMALE	75	75	50	30	20

Partners were asked to declare the quantities, the forms and the sizes of T-shirts (approximately 80 T-shirts each one) they wished to procure and the T-shirts were shipped to all of them by the end of July 2024.

Picture 2: T-shirts of the project in white and denim blue.

Roll-ups quality characteristics

Project's Roll-up maquettes (Picture 3) include an abstract wave pattern, project's logo and tagline in the upper part, brief description of the objectives and expected results of the project in the middle, the code of the project, co-funders' and partners' logos at the bottom.

Both Roll-ups are bilingual: 1 in Greek and English and 1 in Italian and English and their dimensions are 100cmX200cm.

The maquettes were uploaded to project's drive and partners were informed to download and print their own product. They were also uploaded to project's website (node "Project → Deliverables → Work package 5") and are available in the following links:

- Roll-up banner in Greek and English:
<https://www.lifemarenatura.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/LIFE-MareNatura-Roll-Up-100x200-PP-Gr-Eng-low-res-web.pdf>
- Roll-up banner in Italian and English:
<https://www.lifemarenatura.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/LIFE-MareNatura-Roll-Up-100x200-PP-It-Eng-low-res-web.pdf>.

UoC and ARCHELON printed one (1) roll-up in an eco-friendly recyclable tarp mounted on an aluminum mechanism with a storage case. In total

10 GR/ENG and 1 IT/ENG roll ups should be produced.

Picture 3: Roll up maquettes in GR/EN and IT/EN.

Beach flag quality characteristics

Project's Beach Flag (Picture 4) includes an abstract wave pattern at the upper part, the project's logo, title, and tagline in the middle, and the code of the project, co-funders and partners' logos at the bottom, all in English language, common for all partners. The dimensions of the mockup are 270cmX75cm adapted for a specific type of device (eco4m). The maquette was uploaded to the project's drive and partners were informed to download and print their own product. It is also available on the project's website (node "Project → Deliverables → Work package 5")

at the following link:
<https://www.lifemarenatura.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/Beach-flag-pp-LIFE-MareNatura-25062024-low-res-web.pdf>

Picture 4: Beach flag maquette in English.

Project's brochure quality characteristics

The project's Brochure maquettes (3 items: 1 in Greek, 1 in English, and 1 in Italian) are designed for a 12-page multi-fold form (dimensions 30cmX43cm open size & 10cmX21.5cm close). The external view of the leaflet includes the project's title, acronym, code, logo, tagline, project area map, a short description of the project, the target species, its objectives, the tools and methods that will be used by partners in brief and expected results, as well as co-funders and partners' logos, contact information, the URL of the website and Social Media titles. The inner part

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includes the project's basic infographic which presents general info about the target species. The three maquettes of the project can be seen in Picture 5a-c. For the printing a munken polar paper of 120gr was used. In total 34,000 brochures were produced: 25,000 in Greek, 8,000 in English and 1,000 in Italian (Picture 6).

The maquette was uploaded to the project's drive and partners were informed of actions completion. The leaflets are available on project's website (node "Project → Deliverables → Work package 5") in the following links:

- Greek leaflet: https://www.lifemarenatura.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/LIFE-Mare-natura-leaflet-EL-pp2_low-res-web.pdf
- English leaflet: <https://www.lifemarenatura.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/LIFE-Mare-natura-leaflet-E%CE%9D-pp2-low-res-web.pdf>
- Italian leaflet: <https://www.lifemarenatura.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/LIFE-Mare-natura-leaflet-%CE%99%CE%A4-pp3-low-res-web.pdf>

Picture 5a: Greek leaflet mockup.

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Picture 5b: English leaflet mockup.

Picture 5c: Italian leaflet mockup.

Picture 6: The three (3) printed leaflets of the project.